

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

DFG reference number: KL 1240/5-1

Project number: 427446414

Project title: Inverse Analysis in the Context of Non-local Damage and Plasticity Models at High Strain Rates for the Determination and Investigation of Non-classical Material Parameters (Inverse Analysen für nicht-lokale Schädigungs- und Plastizitätsmodelle bei Hochgeschwindigkeitsbeanspruchungen zur Bestimmung und Untersuchung von nicht-klassischen Werkstoffkenngrößen)

Name of the applicant: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Birgit Skrotzki

Official address: Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM), Unter den Eichen 87, 12205 Berlin

Name of the co-applicant: Dr. Vitaliy Kindrachuk

Name of the cooperation partner: N/A

Reporting period (entire funding period): 23.07.2019 - 31.08.2025

Note: The project was originally proposed by Prof. Dietmar Klingbeil and approved in 2019. Since the essential experimental equipment was not available at this time and Prof. Klingbeil was unable to complete the project as planned due to his retirement in 2022, it was transferred in July 2021 to Prof. Skrotzki as the applicant and Dr. Kindrachuk as co-applicant.

2 Summary

This project addressed the reliable prediction of ductile failure in metallic structures under high strain-rate loading. Split-Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) and complementary quasi-static tests were combined with full-field digital image correlation (DIC), enabling spatially resolved characterization of strain localization across a wide range of deformation rates. The combination of experiments and finite-element simulations formed a unified calibration framework and provides a quantitative insight into how the internal length scale within a gradient-enhanced constitutive model affects localization behavior.

The concept was validated using a fine-grained structural steel as reference material. The tailored specimen geometry enabled controlled generation of adiabatic shear bands, captured

by DIC and transferred to the automated inverse identification framework for parameter determination. In parallel, finite-element analyses in Abaqus were repeatedly executed to build the error function from the measured displacements and reaction forces (in the quasi-static case). For predicting the stress response, both the viscoplastic Johnson–Cook (JC) damage model and its gradient-enhanced extension (driven by the non-local equivalent strain) were implemented as VUMAT user subroutines. The identified internal length scale of about 0.07 mm produced consistent predictions of shear-band formation without mesh sensitivity and agreed well with independent EBSD observations and hardness measurements.

As part of the project results, the experimental raw data were documented and partially made publicly available in the Zenodo repository. The established workflow enables future applications, including industrial ones, of gradient-enhanced models to materials and loading conditions that involve strain localization and failure.

Zusammenfassung

Das Projekt befasste sich mit der zuverlässigen Vorhersage des duktilen Versagens metallischer Strukturen unter Hochdehnratenbelastung. Split-Hopkinson-Pressure-Bar-(SHPB)-Versuche und ergänzende quasistatische Tests wurden mit digitaler Bildkorrelation (DIC) im Vollfeldbereich kombiniert, um die Dehnungslokalisierung über einen weiten Bereich von Dehnraten räumlich aufgelöst zu erfassen. Die Verknüpfung von Experiment und Finite-Elemente-Simulation wurde zu einem einheitlichen Kalibrierungskonzept zusammengeführt, das quantitative Einblicke in den Einfluss der inneren Längenskala innerhalb eines gradientenverstärkten konstitutiven Modells auf das Lokalisierungsverhalten liefert.

Das Konzept wurde anhand eines Feinkornstahls als Referenzwerkstoff validiert. Die angepasste Hutprobengeometrie ermöglichte die Erzeugung kontrollierter adiabatischer Scherbänder, die mit DIC erfasst und in das automatisierte inverse Identifikationsverfahren zur Parameterbestimmung überführt wurden. Parallel dazu wurden Finite-Elemente-Analysen in Abaqus iterativ ausgeführt, um die Fehlerfunktion aus gemessenen Verschiebungen und Reaktionskräften, einschließlich des quasistatischen Falls, aufzubauen. Sowohl das viskoplastische Johnson–Cook-Schädigungsmodell als auch seine gradientenverstärkte Erweiterung wurden als VUMAT-Benutzerroutinen implementiert. Die identifizierte innere Längenskala von etwa 0,07 mm führte zu konsistenten Vorhersagen der Scherbandbildung ohne Netzabhängigkeit und stimmte gut mit EBSD- und Härtemessungen überein.

Neben den Modellimplementierungen und Optimierungsskripten wurden die experimentellen Rohdaten dokumentiert und teilweise als Zenodo-Datensatz veröffentlicht. Das resultierende Arbeitskonzept ermöglicht zukünftige, auch industrielle Anwendungen

gradientenverstärkter Modelle auf verschiedene Werkstoffe und Belastungsbedingungen, bei denen Dehnungslokalisierung und Versagen auftreten.

3 Progress Report

3.1 Background and current state of research

Dynamic failure of metallic components subjected to high strain-rate loading is a key concern for safety-critical applications such as aero-engine containment structures and rotating machinery [1]. Reliable design and certification of these require numerical models that can predict adiabatic shear banding (ASB) and the related failure mechanisms. At strain rates above 10^3 s^{-1} , ASBs act as precursors to dynamic fracture, localizing deformation into narrow regions where plastic work is largely converted into heat, leading to thermal softening [2].

Among available constitutive formulations, the JC viscoplastic law is widely used due to its simplicity and ability to capture high-rate and temperature effects [3]. However, local softening formulations are ill-posed in the localization regime, causing mesh dependence and reducing predictive accuracy upon failure [4]. Gradient-enhanced extensions overcome this limitation by introducing an *internal length scale* parameter that regularizes localization and restores well-posed behavior [5]. Early non-local approaches have been successfully demonstrated for quasi-static applications, where they provide mesh-objective results [6].

Despite this progress, the transfer of non-local approaches to dynamic, high-rate problems remains limited. In particular, the experimental calibration and validation of non-local parameters under adiabatic conditions is still underdeveloped. Conventional tensile and compression tests, or common SHPB experiments, produce almost homogeneous strain fields and thus do not trigger the non-local effects needed for parameter identification [7]. As a result, most previous studies determined the internal length scale by trial-and-error or by fitting global force–displacement curves, whereas full-field data suitable for inverse calibration were rarely employed [8]. The present project addressed this gap by establishing an *experiment–model workflow* that (i) generates inhomogeneous, shear-dominated fields at high strain rates, (ii) captures full-field data via DIC suitable for non-local calibration, and (iii) enables inverse finite element identification of the internal length scale and related parameters within a gradient-enhanced JC model.

Recent contributions during the funding period show a clear move beyond classical local modelling toward approaches that consider regularization and microstructural effects. For example, Davaze et al. [9] proposed a dynamic regularization equation for the non-local plastic strain, including viscous and inertial effects, and Clayton [10] incorporated dynamic recrystallization (DRX) into a phase-field model of ASBs, which, as shown in our results, directly addresses the underestimation of temperature rise in ASBs by standard JC

formulations. Modern calibration techniques, such as the physics-informed neural-network method by Hamel et al., that use full-field data, are also notable [11]. While DIC has been used in high-speed testing [12], the applications remain confined to local constitutive models. These developments highlight the relevance of our integrated calibration and validation approach for gradient-enhanced JC modelling and confirm the validity of the original project plan.

3.2 Objectives

The project aimed to improve the numerical modelling of failure in metallic structures under high strain-rate loading by combining modelling and experimental developments in a unified framework. A central element of the project was the further development and application of a non-local material model that, in contrast to conventional local formulations, ensures uniqueness and stability of numerical solutions while providing a more realistic description of strain localization. Because the parameters of non-local models can only be identified under strongly inhomogeneous deformations, the project first focused on designing and testing of tailored specimen geometries for SHPB experiments. These specimens were intended to induce controlled localization zones and thus produce experimental data suitable for the identification of non-local material parameters.

Further, a dedicated parameter identification procedure was developed. This procedure treats the calibration task as a nonlinear optimization problem constrained by the governing field equations. The implementation of the gradient-enhanced material model, including the additional parameter internal length scale, into a finite element tool was essential for the identification procedure, which relied on repetitive, iterative direct simulations of a reduced 2D problem. The internal length scale is a key parameter identified within this framework. A dedicated data interface was created to ensure data transfer between the SHPB tests, particularly displacement-field data obtained via DIC, to the numerical optimization or for verification purposes. Together, these measures established a reliable methodology for the identification and verification of the internal length and so improved the predictive capabilities of high-rate material simulations.

3.3 Description of results and findings

The main outcome of the published work [a] was the development of an integrated experimental-numerical framework and the validation of a specimen geometry suitable for studying ASB formation under high strain-rate loading. A SHPB setup was combined with DIC and high-speed imaging to initiate ASBs at strain rates up to $2 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and to capture the resulting full-field deformation (see Fig. 1). Finite element simulations and preliminary tests led to the identification of a hat-shaped specimen design that enables controlled and reproducible shear localization under near-pure shear conditions.

To establish the model calibration procedure, an extended local Johnson–Cook (JC) viscoplastic model with coupled damage evolution was employed to reproduce the observed localization behavior in fine-grained S355 structural steel. Additional quasi-static tests were performed to extend the validation to a wider strain-rate range and to independently determine the parameters governing rate-insensitive behaviour, as well as those controlling the rate-sensitive response, namely the rate-sensitivity coefficient, thermal-softening exponent, and damage-related parameters. The simulations reproduced the experimentally observed localization patterns and load response with good accuracy, confirming the suitability of the specimen design and the experimental setup. Complementary EBSD analyses revealed pronounced grain refinement and local hardening within the shear bands, thus confirming dynamic recrystallization under adiabatic conditions. The observed local temperature increase of 400 K was about 150 K higher than predicted by the classical Taylor–Quinney assumption.

Fig. 1 From left to right: hat-shaped specimen mounted in the SHPB setup; enlarged view of the notched region with grey-scale speckle pattern for DIC; DIC-measured displacement field (in mm) along the specimen symmetry z -axis and variation of displacement across the shear band (indicated by the red arrow); representative finite-element simulation results showing the spatial distribution of the damage variable (red regions correspond to complete loss of stiffness) and equivalent viscoplastic strain of JC model at strain rates of about $5 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ locally in the shear band as obtained from DIC, and about $5 \times 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the incident bar.

Further important outcomes of the study include the following:

- Scripts to transfer full-field experimental data and FE-predicted responses to enable solution of the inverse problem.
- User-defined UMAT and VUMAT subroutines of JC damage model for implicit and explicit Abaqus solvers, respectively.

Together, these results demonstrate a validated workflow for simulation-assisted SHPB testing of metallic materials and provide the experimental and methodological foundation for the subsequent calibration and validation of gradient-enhanced material models carried out in the second phase of the project.

The paper on the gradient-enhanced extension of the Johnson–Cook (GJC) damage model is, at the time of reporting, under preparation (tentative title [b]). The concept introduces a non-

local equation for the equivalent viscoplastic strain, solved in Ω with homogeneous natural boundary conditions on $\partial\Omega$

$$c_r \nabla^2 \tilde{\lambda}^{vp} = \tilde{\lambda}^{vp} - \lambda^{vp} \text{ in } \partial\Omega, \quad \nabla \tilde{\lambda}^{vp} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega,$$

where λ^{vp} is the local equivalent viscoplastic strain, $\tilde{\lambda}^{vp}$ its non-local counterpart, $c_r = l^2$ is the weighting parameter (equal to the square of the internal length scale), and \mathbf{n} denotes the outward normal on the boundary $\partial\Omega$. The non-local quantity $\tilde{\lambda}^{vp}$ is computed from its local counterpart and subsequently replaces it in the JC model for the evaluation of hardening and damage evolution. For the implementation of the Helmholtz equation in Abaqus Explicit, the analogy with the heat-conduction equation is used by means of the user subroutine VHETVAL. The parameter c_r plays the same role as the thermal conductivity, while the right-hand side acts as an internal heat source. In this formulation, the unknown non-local strain is obtained directly from the computed temperature field. A qualitative difference in the behaviour of the GJC model is illustrated in Fig. 2. During fracture, when the damage variable approaches unity, the viscoplastic strain localizes near the notches. However, the damage variable itself remains spatially smooth because it is driven by the non-local equivalent viscoplastic strain. Consequently, the GJC model avoids mesh sensitivity. This behaviour differs from that of the local formulation, as evident from the comparison of the corresponding field distributions in Fig. 1. In addition, the reaction-force curves in Fig. 2(a) show that increasing the internal length delays fracture and results in a smoother post-peak softening response.

For solving the inverse problem, the DIC snapshots recorded up to complete failure were considered for two SHPB tests conducted at a strain rate of about $5 \times 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the incident bar. It was found that varying only the parameter D_4 (see eq. (7) in [a]), which governs the rate effect in the damage law [a], together with the new parameter c_r , was sufficient to reproduce the DIC displacement fields in the late stages of deformation. Certain parameters, such as the damage exponent k and D_5 required minor fine-tuning. The identified value of the internal length scale is approximately $l = 0.071 \text{ mm}$. This value should not be directly compared with the experimentally observed shear-band width (about 0.4 mm according to hardness measurements). The band width arises naturally in the simulations from the governing equations, once c_r is defined. Therefore, for validation purposes, the simulated hardness profile was compared with the yield-stress distribution predicted by the GJC model, as well as with the measured displacement fields from SHPB tests at different strain rates ($1.1 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $1.8 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the incident bar). As shown in Fig. 3, both comparisons demonstrate good agreement.

Fig. 2. (a) Influence of the internal length scale on the reaction force, illustrated for clarity using a tensile specimen of simple geometry (bottom). (b) Distribution maps of the damage variable d , the local equivalent viscoplastic strain λ^{VP} , and the non-local equivalent viscoplastic strain $\tilde{\lambda}^{VP}$ obtained from a SHPB simulation using the GJC model at an applied strain rate of $5 \times 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the incident bar.

The simulation results show that mesh dependency in the local JC damage model becomes significant only in the final, post-localization stage. This observation is consistent with analytical studies [13] indicating that the effective internal length scale associated with viscoplasticity decreases rapidly at high strain rates and, consequently, as the damage variable approaches unity (see Fig. 4). Hence, the model performs reliably throughout most of the deformation process, while the final stage of failure requires special treatment.

Fig. 3. Variation of the displacement across the shear band: DIC-measured versus FE simulations for (a) the rate of $5 \times 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the incident bar used for parameter optimization and (b) the rate $1.1 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ used for validation. (c) Microhardness values converted to equivalent yield stress using a Tabor factor of 2.86, compared against the predicted values from the local and gradient-enhanced models.

Some recent approaches address this issue by coupling viscoplasticity with phase-field fracture formulations, thereby introducing a ductile–brittle transition. However, the loss of ductility is not supported by our SEM micrographs (see Fig. 6 in [a]), and such coupling would therefore not be physically justified for the present material.

We maintain the ductile framework of the damage-based JC model but introduce a rate-insensitive plastic yield component that becomes dominant in the post-localization stage. In

this formulation, the viscoplastic rate is bounded within the overstress space, whereas the plastic flow rate is governed in a non-local manner (see Fig. 4). In this way, the applicability of the local JC damage model is extended into the post-localization regime. Furthermore, the formulation prevents numerical difficulties that can arise from excessively high overstress values in the exponential viscoplastic yielding law. This model will also be presented in [b].

3.4 Validity and verifiability

To ensure the validity and verifiability of our *simulation* results, we performed a series of verification and validation steps. First, the implementation of the local Johnson–Cook (JC) model was verified by comparing FE results on simple geometries from our user-defined VUMAT routine against Abaqus' built-in JC model under large deformation loading paths. This ensured a consistent treatment of finite deformations and rate-dependent yielding. Since the JC damage model is not available in Abaqus Standard, the UMAT implementation was validated against explicit simulations performed at lower strain rates.

Mesh and time-step sensitivity were systematically assessed through mesh-refinement studies and controlled time increments. Once a suitable discretization was identified for the computationally demanding SHPB simulations, it was applied consistently throughout the program, complemented by stabilization techniques such as hourglass control and early termination at critical damage levels to avoid numerical artifacts. A reduced SHPB bar model was used for parameter optimization and validated against full-length bar simulations and experimentally measured wave profiles. For non-local analyses, particular attention was paid to time-step restrictions arising from the extended CFL condition of the non-local equation.

To validate predictive capabilities, the models were tested on standard benchmark geometries, including 2D notched specimens and unnotched tensile bars. These simulations reproduced plausible damage patterns and shear band formations. For validation of the calibrated model parameters, we compared simulation results against independent experimental data not used for calibration, including tests at different strain rates and cross-checks with microhardness measurements.

3.5 Description of research data

The project generated a comprehensive set of experimental, numerical, and modelling data related to the study of adiabatic shear banding. Experimental data include SHPB strain signals, full-field displacement maps from *GOM Correlate* (stored as *.csv* files), temperature records,

Fig. 4 Typical distributions of the local equivalent viscoplastic strain and the non-local plastic strain at fracture.

EBSD microstructural data, and hardness measurements. All raw and processed data are stored in the institute's project folder together with accompanying metadata files and documentation, ensuring reproducibility. The project folder is accessible to all project members via the institutional network.

Numerical and modelling data comprise Abaqus input and output files used for calibration, as well as user-defined UMAT and VUMAT routines for implicit and explicit solvers. The implemented material routines (Fortran 90 language) and Python-based optimization scripts, along with their respective documentation, are maintained in the institute's internal Git repository (not public) under version control to ensure traceability of changes.

Selected datasets used in the project's publications [a, b] are openly available on Zenodo [e]. The data sets provide raw strain signals, DIC displacement fields, derived boundary conditions, and detailed metadata such as specimen geometry, projectile velocities, and impact pressures. Additional characterisation data, microhardness profiles, and EBSD grain statistics and orientation maps are also included. Other unpublished data or simulation results are available upon reasonable request. For example, EBSD data were shared with the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering at the University of Manchester prior to the publication of the Zenodo record.

All project data is archived on the institute's secure servers, regularly backed up, and will be retained for a minimum of 10 years. The openly available datasets on Zenodo ensure long-term accessibility and citable reference via DOI. The internal Git repositories and local data storage infrastructure provide a reliable basis for further development of the numerical framework and future follow-up studies.

References

1. Carney, K.S., et al., *Jet engine fan blade containment using an alternate geometry*. International Journal of Impact Engineering, 2009. **36**(5): p. 720–728.
2. Karantza, K.D. and D.E. Manolacos, *A Review on the Adiabatic Shear Banding Mechanism in Metals and Alloys Considering Microstructural Characteristics, Morphology and Fracture*. Metals, 2023. **13**(12): p. 1988.
3. Johnson, G.R. and W.H. Cook, *Fracture characteristics of three metals subjected to various strains, strain rates, temperatures and pressures*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 1985. **21**(1): p. 31–48.
4. Pijaudier-Cabot, G. and A. Benallal, *Strain localization and bifurcation in a nonlocal continuum*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 1993. **30**(13): p. 1761–1775.
5. Poh, L.H. and S. Swaddiwudhipong, *Gradient-enhanced softening material models*. International Journal of Plasticity, 2009. **25**(11): p. 2094–2121.
6. Tvergaard, V. and A. Needleman, *Effects of nonlocal damage in porous plastic solids*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 1995. **32**(8): p. 1063–1077.
7. Carmeliet, J., *Optimal estimation of gradient damage parameters from localization phenomena in quasi-brittle materials*. Mechanics of Cohesive-frictional Materials, 1999. **4**(1): p. 1–16.

8. Geers, M.G.D., R. de Borst, and T. Peijs, *Mixed numerical-experimental identification of non-local characteristics of random-fibre-reinforced composites*. Composites Science and Technology, 1999. **59**(10): p. 1569–1578.
9. Davaze, V., et al., *A non-local damage approach compatible with dynamic explicit simulations and parallel computing*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2021. **228**: p. 110999.
10. Clayton, J.D., *Phase-field theory of adiabatic shear*. Acta Mechanica, 2025.
11. Hamel, C.M., K.N. Long, and S.L.B. Kramer, *Calibrating constitutive models with full-field data via physics informed neural networks*. Strain, 2023. **59**(2): p. e12431.
12. Gkolfinopoulos, I. and N. Chijiwa, *Determination of Johnson–Cook Material and Failure Model Constants for High-Tensile-Strength Tendon Steel in Post-Tensioned Concrete Members*. Applied Sciences, 2022. **12**(15): p. 7774.
13. Flatten, A., *Lokale und nicht-lokale Modellierung und Simulation thermomechanischer Lokalisierung mit Schädigung für metallische Werkstoffe unter Hochgeschwindigkeitsbeanspruchungen*, 2008, Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung BAM: Berlin.

4. Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

- a. S. Jentsch, D. Stock, R. Häcker, B. Skrotzki, R. D. Kamachali, D. Klingbeil, V. M. Kindrachuk, *Shear Band Formation with Split Hopkinson Bar Experiments*, Int. J. Mech. Sci., **284** (2024) 109749, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimecsci.2024.109749>
- b. S. Jentsch, B. Skrotzki, R. D. Kamachali, D. Klingbeil, V. M. Kindrachuk, *Gradient-Enhanced Constitutive Modeling of Adiabatic Shear Bands*, in preparation for Int. J. Impact Eng.

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

- c. S. Jentsch, D. Stock, R. Häcker, D. Klingbeil, V. M. Kindrachuk, *Numerical and Experimental Investigations on Metal Shear Band Formation at High Strain Rates with a Hopkinson Bar Setup*, oral presentation, GAMM Annual Meeting 2023, Dresden, 30 May 2023.
- d. S. Jentsch, D. Stock, R. Häcker, B. Skrotzki, R. D. Kamachali, D. Klingbeil, V. M. Kindrachuk, *Experimental and Numerical Studies on Shear Band Formation at High Strain Rates*, oral presentation, European Conference of Fracture 2024, Zagreb, 26 August 2024.
- e. S. Jentsch, D. Stock, R. Häcker, B. Skrotzki, R. D. Kamachali, D. Klingbeil, V. M. Kindrachuk, *Data Set to SHPB Investigations of S355 Specimens and Complementary Characterization Methods*, Zenodo (2025), [10.5281/zenodo.17591439](https://zenodo.org/record/17591439)

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

None.